

ethyl parathion. In a concentration of 0.1% and 0.5% the mean K. D. (knock down) Time (h) of ethyl parathion is 4.5 and 5.5 respectively. All the compounds were tested but the compounds No. 8, 10, 12, 17, 19 and 20 exhibited appreciable insecticidal activity.

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Preparation and Fungitoxicity of Substituted Sulphamidophenyl-O-Alkyl Xanthates

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THIRTY two substituted sulphamidophenyl-O-alkyl xanthates have been prepared and evaluated *in vitro* against *Alternaria tenuis* and *Helminthosporium sativum*. A relation between fungitoxicity and structure has also been established.

A large number of salt of O-alkyl derivatives of xanthates have been reported in recent years to possess fungicidal activity against conidia of *M. fructicola*^{1,2}. The potassium xanthates up to C₈

were tested for toxicity in mice and Tubifex-tubifex worm³. They have also been used in the concentration of ores⁴ and cosmetics⁵. A perusal of literature on xanthates revealed that mostly they have been used as metallic salts with very little emphasis on the esters. Benzyl butyl xanthate is used as an insecticide for red spider⁶. Earlier some halogeno-nitrophenyl esters of -O-methyl and -O-ethyl xanthates were found to be toxic⁷.

This paper deals with the synthesis of substituted sulphamidophenyl-O-alkyl xanthates with efficacy results and structure-activity relationship. They have been prepared by the condensation of potassium salt of -O-alkyl xanthate(I) and diazotised sulphanilamide(II) in aqueous solution at 0-15°. The intermediate diazo derivative(III) loses nitrogen and is converted into the corresponding substituted sulphamidophenyl-O-alkyl xanthate(IV).

Experimental

Potassium salt of -O-alkyl xanthate: Prepared according to the method given in the literature⁸.

O-alkyl-substituted Sulphamidophenyl Xanthate: Substituted sulphanilamide (0.01M) dissolved in concentrated hydrochloric acid (10 ml) was diluted with water (40 ml). The resulting solution was cooled to 0° and treated with a solution of sodium nitrite (0.01M) dissolved in water (10 ml). The solution of diazonium salt of sulphanilamide so obtained was then added dropwise to a well cooled solution of potassium-O-alkyl xanthate (0.01 M). The stirring was continued for half an hour. The solution was then heated on a water bath till the evolution of nitrogen ceased. On cooling, substituted sulphamidophenyl-O-alkyl xanthates separated out. These were filtered and crystallised from methyl alcohol. The physical data of these compounds are given in Table 1 alongwith their fungitoxicity.

Fungitoxicity of substituted sulphamidophenyl-O-alkyl xanthates:

These compounds were tested for their anti-fungal activity against *Alternaria tenuis* and *Helminthosporium sativum* by spore germination method⁹. Ed₅₀ values were determined from data for five con-

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centrations of the test compounds on a log probit scale. The results are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA AND FUNGITOXICITY OF SUBSTITUTED SULPHAMIDOPHENYL-O-ALKYL XANTHATES

Compound	R	R'	M.P.(°C)	10 ⁵ ED ₅₀ (M)
1.	CH ₃	H	182	164.0
2.	"	-acetyl	120	420.0
3.	"	-2-thiazolyl	176	33.0
4.	"	-2-pyridyl	157	210.0
5.	"	-2-pyrimidyl	187	30.0
6.	"	-2-(4-methyl)pyrimidyl	150	200.0
7.	"	2-(4,6-dimethyl)-pyrimidyl	132	200.0
8.	"	-2-guanidyl	95	37.0
9.	C ₂ H ₅	-H	180	170.0
10.	"	-COCH ₃	69	549.0
11.	"	-2-thiazolyl	162	37.0
12.	"	-2-pyridyl	94	250.0
13.	"	-2-pyrimidyl	223	33.0
14.	"	-2-(4-methyl)-pyrimidyl	198	210.0
15.	"	-2-(4,6-dimethyl)-pyrimidyl	205	240.0
16.	"	-2-guanidyl	140	56.0
17.	C ₃ H ₇	-H	219	200.0
18.	"	-acetyl	182	575.0
19.	"	-2-thiazolyl	159	63.0
20.	"	-2-pyridyl	139	290.0
21.	"	-2-pyrimidyl	147	55.0
22.	"	-2-(4-methyl)-pyrimidyl	181	420.0
23.	"	2-(2,6-dimethyl)-pyrimidyl	202	450.0
24.	"	-2-guanidyl	120	72.0
25.	C ₄ H ₉	-H	139	210.0
26.	"	-acetyl	90	610.0
27.	"	-2-thiazolyl	176	64.0
28.	"	-2-pyridyl	96	300.0
29.	"	-2-pyrimidyl	209	63.0
30.	"	-2-(4-methyl)-pyrimidyl	215	450.0
31.	"	-2-(4,6-dimethyl)-pyrimidyl	219	575.0
32.	"	-2 guan'dyl	100	80.0

substitution of sulphamidophenyl by -2-acetyl, -2-pyridyl, 2-(4-methyl pyrimidyl) and -2-(4,6-dimethyl-pyrimidyl) reduces the activity. In fact -2-thiazolyl, -2-pyrimidyl and -2-guanidyl sulphamidophenyl-O-alkyl xanthates are the only promising fungitoxicants in this class of compound. The above observation is confirmed from Table 1. This is evident from the following order of activity :

The 2-acetyl substituted compound is totally inactive.

In the -O-alkyl moiety the presence of lower alkyl group generally increases the fungitoxicity. Thus it has been seen that there is slight fall in the activity when methyl group is replaced by ethyl group, but there is a sharp fall in the activity when replaced by propyl and butyl groups. Table 1 shows that the order of fungitoxicity is as given below :

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Results and Discussion

Structure-Activity Relationship : From Ed₅₀ value (Table 1), the most active compound of this series was found to be 2-pyrimidyl sulphamidophenyl-O-methyl xanthate (compound No. 5) which is followed by -2-thiazolyl (No. 3). It appears that